

Mixed Ligand Complexes of Nickel(II) with Alkyl-1-amidino-2-thioureas

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Mixed ligand complexes of nickel(II) with *S*-alkyl-1-amidino-2-thiourea (HSRATU) and *N*-alkyl-1-amidino-2-thiourea (HNRATU) and pyridine (py), γ -picoline (γ -pic), quinoline (Qu) and imidazole (Imd) have been isolated from methanol medium and characterised mainly by electronic spectra. The green six-coordinated complexes were paramagnetic.

THE ligand amidinothiourea HATU (1) forms both NN and SN bonded complexes. Its *S*-alkyl derivatives, HSRATU (2), and *N*-alkyl derivatives, HNRATU (3) behave only as NN and SN donor ligand, respectively. All these ligands, however, form square-planar complexes with nickel²⁺. The aim of the paper is to investigate the adducts of these square-planar complexes with basic donor ligands like pyridine, picoline, quinoline and imidazole on the one hand and neutral donor solvents like DMSO and DMF on the other. Biguanides and amidinoisourea which are very similar to these ligands do not form any octahedral complexes^{6,7}.

Experimental

Analytical grade reagents and pure distilled solvents were used throughout the work.

Preparation of complexes: The nickel complex (0.01 mol) of HNRATU or HSRATU was dissolved in methanol followed by addition of heterocyclic base (0.02 mol). It was then evaporated slowly in an inert atmosphere. The complexes separated as green crystals were filtered, recrystallised from chloroform and dried in an inert atmosphere.

Metal, halogen and sulphur were determined by semi-microanalytical methods. Electronic and IR spectral studies, magnetic and conductance measurements were carried out in Carry 17D and Beckman IR-12 spectrophotometers, Gouy balance and Philips conductivity bridge, respectively.

Results and Discussion

HATU (1) forms two different square-planar complex of nickel²⁺. The yellow NN bonded neutral complex, isolated in aqueous medium, is insoluble in all solvents, and it does not form any salt. The red SN bonded ionic complex, isolated in acetone medium, is soluble in methanol, ethanol and DMF. The red solution, on standing in air, changes to yellow from which NN bonded complexes of HATU are isolated. On addition of heterocyclic base to the red solution, the conversion to yellow NN bonded complex takes place very rapidly and no adduct is obtained. The red compound, on being dissolved in neutral donor solvents like methanol, ethanol, DMSO and dioxane produces a green precipitate. The green compound can also be obtained by addition of nickel chloride and HATU in 1 : 2 molar ratio in these solvents. The compound is diamagnetic and insoluble in all solvents. Analytical data of this green compound does not correspond to any simple stoichiometric ratio of metal and ligand. Probably it is a highly polymeric compound and the chloride atom plays a very important role in this polymerisation as no such compound formation takes place when nickel bromide is used instead of nickel chloride.

HNRATU (3) and HSRATU (2) form red SN bonded and yellow NN bonded square-planar ionic complexes with nickel, respectively (Table 1). Addition of heterocyclic base to the solution of these bis-ligand compounds in methanol produces a green coloured solution from which the adduct of the bases are isolated. Analytical data of these adducts correspond to six-coordinated complexes with two molecules of base attached to square-planar complexes. Magnetic moment values (2.8–3.0 B.M.) are as expected for two unpaired electron system. Molar conductance data in chloroform indicate them to be 1 : 2 complexes. The complexes lose

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TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				$\mu_{\text{eff}}^{\text{B}}$ B.M.	$\Lambda_{1000}^{\text{D}}$ $\Omega \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$
	Ni	N	S	OI		
[Ni(HSMATU) ₂ (py) ₂]Cl ₂	10.45 (10.60)	25.67 (25.59)	11.61 (11.70)	13.15 (12.98)	2.95	218
[Ni(HSMATU) ₂ (γ -pic) ₂]Cl ₂	10.10 (10.00)	24.19 (24.13)	11.19 (11.03)	12.12 (12.24)	2.91	230
[Ni(HSEATU) ₂ (py) ₂]Cl ₂	10.21 (10.13)	24.59 (24.47)	11.29 (11.17)	12.29 (12.39)	2.98	205
[Ni(HSEATU) ₂ (γ -pic) ₂]Cl ₂	9.71 (9.74)	23.65 (23.52)	10.79 (10.75)	11.85 (11.95)	2.93	235
[Ni(HSEATU) ₂ (Qu) ₂]Cl ₂	8.41 (8.51)	20.59 (20.58)	9.30 (9.41)	10.47 (10.44)	2.90	240
[Ni(HSEATU) ₂ (Imd) ₂]Cl ₂	10.21 (10.36)	29.86 (29.00)	11.79 (11.68)	12.81 (12.68)	2.98	286
[Ni(HNMATU) ₂ (py) ₂]Cl ₂	10.31 (10.60)	25.40 (25.59)	11.81 (11.70)	13.21 (12.98)	2.87	235
[Ni(HNMATU) ₂ (γ -pic) ₂]Cl ₂	9.95 (10.10)	24.05 (24.13)	11.17 (11.03)	12.30 (12.24)	2.95	241
[Ni(HNEATU) ₂ (py) ₂]Cl ₂	10.08 (10.12)	24.41 (24.47)	11.31 (11.17)	12.21 (12.39)	2.91	240
[Ni(HNEATU) ₂ (γ -pic) ₂]Cl ₂	9.80 (9.74)	23.41 (23.52)	10.61 (10.75)	11.87 (11.95)	2.98	245
[Ni(HNEATU) ₂ (Qu) ₂]Cl ₂	8.92 (8.45)	20.49 (20.46)	9.45 (9.32)	10.59 (10.55)	2.95	235
[Ni(HNEATU) ₂ (Imd) ₂]Cl ₂	10.20 (10.26)	29.79 (29.86)	11.50 (11.58)	12.42 (12.59)	2.93	245

^aAt 303 K. ^bIn solvent ...

two molecules of base on being exposed to air for 5–24 h, forming the original square-planar complexes. This indicates that six-coordinated complexes are not very stable in air. Neutral donor solvents like DMSO and dioxane produce no such adduct of these square-planar complexes.

In the mixed ligand complexes, new ir bands appear at ~1585, ~1240 and ~620 cm⁻¹ due to the heterocyclic base rings. Other features were comparable to those of the simple bis complexes¹. The two types of complexes (SN and NN bonded) differ in their band position in the visible region. The NN bonded complexes displayed three well defined bands, while the SN bonded complexes showed an additional shoulder over the second band. The 10500–10950, 16820–17950 cm⁻¹ and 28150–29010 cm⁻¹ bands are assigned to ⁸A_{2g}→⁸T_{2g}, ⁸A_{2g}→⁸T_{1g}(F) and ⁸A_{2g}→⁸T_{1g}(P) transitions, respectively. The bands observed beyond 30000 cm⁻¹ are assigned to charge transfer processes. But the ligand bands are obscured by the solvent bands. The electronic spectral data for pure ligands are as follows: HATU, 46950, 41670 and 36760; HSEATU, 46510 and 41670; HNEATU, 47609, 46322 and 37735 cm⁻¹. The band observed at 36000–38000 cm⁻¹ for pure ligand is due to C=S group which is not observed in the complexes⁸.

The ligand field energy values 25270, 22916 and 20818 cm⁻¹, respectively, for [Ni(ATU)₂], [Ni(HSEATU)₂]Cl₂ and [Ni(HNEATU)₂]Cl₂, suggest

nickel(II) in the complex of ligand 1 is under the influence of stronger field than those with 2 and 3. Again, the extensive delocalisation between metal and ligand 1 results a stable square-planar complex. In the complexes of 2 and 3 the scope for such delocalisation is low due to the presence of alkyl group. Thus both these factors help the complexes of ligands 2 and 3 to attain six-coordination. Biguanides, amidinoisourea and its N-alkyl derivatives which are very similar to those of NN donor ligands 1, do not form octahedral complexes of nickel^{6,7}.

Therefore, 1-amidino-2-thiourea, due to its stronger ligand field and the scope for extensive electron delocalisation does not form octahedral nickel(II) complexes while its S-alkyl and N-alkyl derivatives form such complexes.

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